

Thermodynamics of Micellization. Part—I. Micelle Formation of CTAB, NaLS and Triton-X-100 in DMF-H₂O, DMSO-H₂O, Dioxane-H₂O and MeOH-H₂O Systems by Dye Incorporation Method

L. PANDA and G. B. BEHERA*

Post Graduate Department of Chemistry, Sambalpur University, Burla-768 017

Manuscript received 16 April 1984, accepted 8 November 1984

The critical micelle concentration (cmc) of the surfactants cetyl trimethylammonium bromide (CTAB), sodium lauryl sulphate (NaLS), and polyoxyethylene(9.5) p-1,1,3,3-tetramethyl butyl phenol (Triton-X-100) have been determined spectrophotometrically by dye incorporation method at 25° in DMF-water, DMSO-water, dioxane-water and methanol-water systems. The cmc values obtained in this method compare well with the values obtained by other methods. It has been found that the cmc of all the surfactants increase with increasing mole fraction of the organic solvent and beyond a particular solvent composition no micelle formation is found to take place. The change of cmc with solvent composition has, however, been rationalised on the basis of co-solvent effect on water structure and change in free energy of micellization. The thermodynamic parameters of the process of micellization have been evaluated for all the systems.

AGGREGATION of amphiphiles leading to the formation of micelles is important in many chemical and biological processes¹. Deaggregation of micelles involve exposure of the non-polar portion of the surfactant molecules. This is similar to the denaturation of proteins in which the non-polar amino acid side chains are exposed to the solvent. There have been many studies on the effect of protein denaturants on micelle stability. One of the methods of such a study is the determination of critical micelle concentration (cmc) in presence of co-solvents. These co-solvents include urea, acetone, methanol, dioxane, ethylene glycol, glycerol and various other amides for ionic surfactants² and non-ionic surfactants³. Lawrence and Pearson⁴, and Singh and Swarup⁵ have used 1-alcohols and urea as co-solvents in their studies. Manabe and Coda⁶ have seen the effect of poly-(oxyethylene)alkyl ether, alkane diols and alkanols on the cmc of SDS. Ternier *et al.*⁷ have used acetone, Jean and Ache⁸ have used benzene, benzyl alcohol, n-hexane and 1-hexanol as co-solvents. Several groups of workers⁹⁻²¹ have investigated the surfactant aggregation in polar non-aqueous solvents by surface tension, conductivity, viscosity and freezing point methods. This paper deals with the determination of cmc of CTAB, NaLS and T-X-100 by dye incorporation method in solvent systems like DMF-H₂O, DMSO-H₂O, dioxane-H₂O and MeOH-H₂O with a view to compare the results obtained by other methods and to evaluate the thermodynamic parameters of the process.

Experimental

Materials : Cetyl trimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) and sodium lauryl sulphate (both B.D.H.) were used after purification by the method of Duynstee and Grunwald²². Triton-X-100 was of B.D.H. (England) and was used without further purification. The dye, methyl violet (E. Merk, Germany) was used as such. DMF, DMSO and methanol were of E. Merk spectro-grade and were used as such. 1,4-Dioxane was of Sisco-Chem and was used after purification²³. All solutions were prepared in triple-distilled water, preserved in glass apparatus of corning grade and used within seven days of their preparation.

Measurements : All measurements were carried out spectrophotometrically in a Carl Zeiss Jena VSU-2P spectrophotometer equipped with thermostated cell holders at 25° at the λ_{max} of the dye (580 nm) and at a fixed dye concentration, ($10^{-5} M$) with varying concentration of surfactants at different mole fractions of the organic component in the aquo-organic solvent systems. All the data recorded are an average of three to four sets of readings and each set of experiment was followed within a range of 10-15 concentrations of the surfactants.

All the solutions for measurement were bottled in corning stoppered bottles and were shaken for 2 h to ensure complete incorporation (adsorption) of the dye into the surfactant aggregates. The bottles were then thermostated for 0.5 h to equilibrate

with the experimental temperature. All absorbances were taken in pre-thermostated 1 cm quartz cells by transferring a portion of the contents of the bottle into the cells. A break in the plot of absorbance vs [surfactant] indicated the micelle formation and the point of intersection of the two lines corresponded to the cmc value. A linear plot was taken to be an indication of no micelle formation. Representative plots of absorbance vs [surfactant] of CTAB, NaLS and Triton-X-100 are given in Figs. 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

Results and Discussion

In all these experiments the concentration of the dye is so small that no influence of the dye on the micellization is assumed. The cmc values of CTAB, NaLS and T-X-100 determined by dye incorporation method in water are given in Tables 1-4. The values agree well with the literature values²⁴.

It is obvious that the cmc values in water either increase or decrease with increasing concentration

Fig. 1. Plot of optical density vs concentration of hexadecyl trimethyl ammonium bromide in presence of methyl violet in water—*N,N*-dimethyl formamide solution at 25°

Fig. 2. Plot of optical density vs concentration of sodium lauryl sulphate in presence of methyl violet in dioxane-water solvent system at 25°.

Fig. 3. Plot of optical density vs concentration of Triton-X-100 (in volume%) in presence of methyl violet in water-DMF solution at 25°. \odot mole fraction of DMF=0.025.

of organic co-solvent. But here the results showed an increase in the cmc values with increasing concentration of organic co-solvent, like DMF, DMSO and dioxane. With increasing amount of methanol as the co-solvent a decrease is noted first followed by an increase in the cmc value. The results obtained by the dye incorporation method in presence of co-solvents compare well with the literature values obtained by the other accepted methods²⁴⁻²⁸ (see Tables). A plot of mole fraction of the organic co-solvent ($X_{\text{cosolvent}}$) or dielectric constant of the solvent system vs the cmc values show breaks at different values of the mole fraction of the co-solvent/dielectric constant of the solvent system. These values are given in Table 5. It is also observed that beyond the break points the cmc values increase rapidly for ionic surfactants where as it remains almost constant for nonionic surfactants. Though a definite view on this observation can not be put forward at this stage, it is believed that the micelle structure, beyond the break point, of the nonionic surfactant remain unchanged within a range of mixed solvent

TABLE 1—CHANGE IN CRITICAL MICELLE CONCENTRATION (CMC), FREE ENERGY OF MICELLIZATION (ΔG_m^0) AND FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER (ΔG_{tr}^0) OF SURFACTANTS IN DMF-WATER SOLVENT SYSTEM AT 25° BY DYE INCORPORATION METHOD

Vol of DMF %	Mole fraction of DMF	Dielectric constant of medium D at 25°	CTAB			NaLS			Triton-X-100		
			cmc* $\times 10^4 M$	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	cmc $\times 10^3 M$	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	cmc vol %	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹
0	0.00	78.4	9.1(9.2)	4.14	0	8.20	2.84	0.00	0.55	0.35	0.00
5	0.012	78.0	15.0	3.85	0.59	12.10	2.61	0.46	0.68	0.22	0.25
10	0.025	77.5	21.5(20.0)	3.63	1.01	16.30	2.43	0.81	0.92	0.05	0.60
15	0.039	77.0	26.20	3.52	1.25	20.50	2.30	1.08	1.00	0.00	0.70
20	0.054	76.5	33.0(35.5)	3.38	1.52	25.00	2.18	1.32	1.00	0.00	0.70
30	0.091	76.0	55.0(63.1)	3.08	2.13	50.00	2.07	1.53	1.00	0.00	0.70
40	0.134	75.0	101.0(100.0)	2.72	2.85	45.00	1.83	2.01	1.00	0.00	0.70
50	0.189	74.0	125.5(126.0)	2.59	3.10	—	—	—	—	—	—
60	0.259	71.0	298.0(295.0)	2.08	4.13	—	—	—	—	—	—
70	0.353	66.0	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

* Data in parenthesis from Ref. 25.

TABLE 2—CHANGE IN CRITICAL MICELLE CONCENTRATION (CMC), FREE ENERGY OF MICELLIZATION (ΔG_m^0) AND FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER (ΔG_{tr}^0) OF SURFACTANTS IN DMSO-WATER SOLVENT SYSTEM AT 25° BY DYE INCORPORATION METHOD

Vol of DMSO %	Mole fraction of DMSO	Dielectric constant of medium D at 25°	CTAB			NaLS			Triton-X-100		
			cmc* $\times 10^4 M$	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	cmc $\times 10^3 M$	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	cmc vol %	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹
0	0.00	78.4	9.10	4.14	0.00	8.20	2.84	0.00	0.55	0.355	0.00
5	0.013	77.00	11.60	4.00	0.28	10.00	2.73	0.23	0.62	0.283	0.14
10	0.027	74.0	13.60 (13.13)	3.90	0.47	12.00	2.62	0.45	0.70	0.211	0.28
15	0.043	72.5	16.90	3.78	0.73	14.50	2.50	0.67	0.82	0.117	0.47
20	0.059	71.0	21.00 (21.42)	3.65	0.99	17.00	2.41	0.86	0.95	0.030	0.64
25	0.078	69.5	27.00	3.50	1.28	20.00	2.31	1.05	1.00	0.00	0.70
30	0.098	68.0	31.50 (29.92)	3.41	1.47	24.00	2.20	1.27	1.00	0.00	0.70
35	0.120	66.5	38.00	3.30	1.69	28.20	2.11	1.46	1.00	0.00	0.70
40	0.144	65.0	42.00 (50.66)	3.24	1.81	32.50	2.03	1.63	1.00	0.00	0.70
45	0.171	63.5	59.20	3.04	2.21	38.0	1.94	1.81	—	—	—
50	0.202	62.0	68.00 (72.23)	2.95	2.38	—	—	—	—	—	—
55	0.236	60.0	88.50	2.80	2.68	—	—	—	—	—	—
60	0.275	59.0	119.50 (137.20)	2.62	3.05	—	—	—	—	—	—

* Data in parenthesis from, L. G. Ionescu, T. Tokuhiko, B. J. Czerniawski, Proceeding of 52nd. A. C. S. Colloid and Surface Science Symposium, Knoxville, Tennessee, 1978.

TABLE 3—CHANGE IN CRITICAL MICELLE CONCENTRATION (CMC), FREE ENERGY OF MICELLIZATION (ΔG_m^0) AND FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER (ΔG_{tr}^0) OF SURFACTANTS IN DIOXANE-WATER SOLVENT SYSTEM AT 25° BY DYE INCORPORATION METHOD

Vol of Dioxane %	Mole fraction of Dioxane	Dielectric constant of medium D at 25°	CTAB			NaLS			Triton-X-100		
			cmc $\times 10^4 M$	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	cmc $\times 10^3 M$	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mole ⁻¹	cmc vol %	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹
0	0.00	78.40	9.1	4.14	0	8.2	2.85	0	0.55	0.355	0
5	0.011	74.50	12.0	3.98	0.32	10.5	2.69	0.29	0.70	0.211	0.28
10	0.024	69.90	16.0	3.81	0.67	12.5	2.59	0.49	0.84	0.103	0.50
15	0.036	65.00	24.0	3.57	1.15	16.5	2.43	0.82	1.00	0.00	0.70
20	0.050	60.79	33.5	3.32	1.54	23.0	2.23	1.22	1.20	-0.10	0.92
25	0.065	56.50	42.0	3.24	1.81	31.0	2.06	1.57	1.50	-0.24	1.19
30	0.082	51.90	71.0	2.93	2.43	43.0	1.86	1.96	1.65	-0.29	1.30
35	0.102	47.00	101.5	2.72	2.85	—	—	—	—	—	—
40	0.123	42.98	130.0	2.57	3.15	—	—	—	—	—	—
50	0.174	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—	—

TABLE 4—CHANGE IN CRITICAL MICELLE CONCENTRATION (CMC), FREE ENERGY OF MICELLIZATION (ΔG_m^0) AND FREE ENERGY OF TRANSFER (ΔG_{tr}^0) OF SURFACTANTS IN METHANOL-WATER SOLVENT SYSTEM AT 25° BY DYE INCORPORATION METHOD

Vol of Methanol %	Mole fraction of Methanol	Dielectric constant of medium D at 25°	CTAB			NaLS			Triton-X-100		
			cmc $\times 10^4 M$	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	cmc* $\times 10^3 M$	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	cmc Vol %	$-\Delta G_m^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta G_{tr}^0$ kcal mol ⁻¹
0	0.00	78.4	9.2	4.14	0.00	8.1	2.85	0	0.55	0.35	0.00
5	0.023	74.0	11.0	4.03	0.21	6.2	3.01	-0.31	0.57	0.33	0.04
10	0.047	72.0	12.6	3.95	0.37	7.0	2.94	-0.17	0.62	0.28	0.14
15	0.073	69.0	14.5	3.87	0.53	7.8	2.87	-0.04	0.68	0.22	0.25
20	0.100	67.0	16.2	3.80	0.67	8.4	2.83	0.04	0.75	0.17	0.36
25	0.129	65.0	18.0	3.74	0.79	9.0 (9.0)	2.79	0.12	0.82	0.11	0.47
30	0.160	62.5 _d	20.8	3.65	0.96	10.2	2.71	0.27	0.90	0.06	0.58
35	0.193	60.5	24.2	3.56	1.14	11.6	2.64	0.42	0.90	0.06	0.58
40	0.228	58.0	30.0	3.44	1.40	13.8	2.53	0.63	0.90	0.06	0.58
45	0.267	56	No aggregates	—	—	No aggregates	No aggregates	—	—	—	—

* Data in parenthesis from Ref. 28.

TABLE 5—OCCURRENCE OF BREAK POINTS AT DIFFERENT DIELECTRIC CONSTANT (D) VALUES AND CMC VALUES OF SURFACTANTS

Organic co-solvent	Name of the Surfactant					
	CTAB		NaLS		Triton-X-100	
	D	cmc $\times 10^4$	D	cmc $\times 10^3$	D	cmc vol %
DMF	76.8	30.0	—	—	77.0	1
DMSO	63.2	47.0	70.4	16.5	68.8	1
MeOH	62.4	21.0	60.4	11.0	62.3	0.9
Dioxane	58.4	33	63.6	17.0	64.5	1

composition but with ionic surfactants the structure perhaps continuously change. It has been observed that plot of viscosity vs weight% of co-solvent shows a maximum at 40% for methanol-water³⁰, 60% for dioxane-water³⁰ and 70% for DMSO-water³¹. This appearance of a maximum indicates a change in the structure in the solvent system. The break points in the present study appear at much below perhaps because the system becomes a three-component one.

The amphiphiles form micelles at a particular concentration (cmc) of the surfactant because of the balance between the attractive hydrophobic interaction of the long chain hydrocarbon tails and the repulsive forces between the ionic head groups. Addition of an organic co-solvent decreases the polarity (lowers the dielectric constant) of the medium, as a result, the hydrophobic interaction between the hydrocarbon tails decrease and hence, the cmc is observed at a higher concentration of the surfactants. The study of cmc by adding co-solvent can be compared to protein denaturation. The increase in cmc of all the surfactants may mean that the co-solvents can be considered as structure breakers, though there are some short comings to this rationalizations^{32,33}. These co-solvents are not penetrating ones, since penetrating co-solvents usually lower cmc by mixed micelle formation, though in some cases dioxane has been found to be a penetrating additive³⁴. The aggregation size of the surfactants has not been determined in the

present investigation but Muller³⁴⁻³⁶ has shown evidence for decreased aggregation number in the presence of co-solvents using ¹⁹F nmr and a monomer-n-mer model for aggregation. Rapid increase of cmc after a particular concentration of the organic co-solvent may be due to (i) a change in the structure of the solvent system, (ii) a change in the micellar structure or (iii) a change in the aggregate size.

The ΔG_m° values, the standard free energy of transfer of a monomer from the bulk phase to the micelle of average size 'm', have been calculated for different solvent systems and for different surfactants by following Tanford's treatment³⁷. The contributing factors to the ΔG_m° values are ΔU_m° , due to hydrophobic interactions which is negative and W_m , due to head group interactions which is positive. The values of ΔG_m° , ΔU_m° and W_m for all the systems are given in Tables 1-4.

The standard free energy of transfer of a hydrocarbon tail of a monomer from the bulk phase the micelle of average size 'm', i.e. ΔG_{tr}° can be calculated from the Miyagishi equation³⁸ (equation 1).

$$\Delta G_{tr}^\circ = 2RT \ln \frac{cmc(H_2O)}{cmc(\text{mixed solvent})} + 2RW \ln \frac{f(H_2O)}{f(\text{mixed solvent})} \quad (1)$$

where $cmc(H_2O)$ refers to the cmc of the surfactant in pure water, $cmc(\text{mixed solvent})$ refers to the cmc of the surfactant at a particular solvent composition, $f(H_2O)$ refers to the activity coefficient of the surfactant in water, and $f(\text{mixed solvent})$ refers to the activity coefficient of the surfactant at a particular solvent composition. The ΔG_{tr}° values of the different solvent systems of all the surfactants have been calculated with one assumption, that $f(H_2O) = f(\text{mixed solvent})$ and given in Tables 1-4. The ΔG_m° values increase for all the surfactants in all the solvent-systems and a plot of ΔG_m° vs $X_{\text{cosolvent}}$ (Figs. 4-6) is a straight line except in

Fig. 4. CTAB system.

case of DMF. In DMF a break is observed at a mole fraction of 0.134. The increase in ΔG_m° values clearly indicates that the addition of co-solvent makes the micelle unstable.

Fig. 5. NaLS system.

Fig. 6. Triton-X100 system.

It has been observed by Wetlaufer *et al.*³⁹ that for the transfer of the hydrocarbon gases (except methane) from water to 7M urea have negative ΔG_{tr}° values but positive ΔH_{tr}° and ΔS_{tr}° values. Hence, the effect of hydrocarbon tails dominate on the transfer function ($\Delta \Delta U_m^\circ \gg \Delta W_m^\circ$). This can be accounted for qualitatively if one ignores the co-solvent effects on aggregate size, counter ion binding and standard chemical potential of micelle. The same trend has also been observed by Tanford *et al.*⁴⁰ for the transfer of the nonpolar amino acid side chains into aqueous urea and into aqueous ethylene glycol. Treiner *et al.*⁴¹ have determined ΔG_{tr}° for decyl trimethyl ammonium chloride from water to aqueous acetone using vapour pressure measurements and obtained a similar type of trend.

It is not easy to make a complete analysis of the influence of co-solvent in view of the large co-solvent induced changes in aggregate size and composition, co-solvent's ability to stabilise or destabilise the monomer and above all co-solvent induced changes in the structure of the aggregate.

Acknowledgement

The authors express their thanks U.G.C., New Delhi for the grant of Teacher Fellowship and Government of Orissa for granting leave to one of them (L.P.).

References

1. L. MAGID in "Solution Chemistry of Surfactants", ed. K. L. MITTAL, Plenum Press, New York, 1979, Vol. 1.
2. M. F. EMERSON and A. HOLTZER, *J. Phys. Chem*, 1967, 71, 3320.
3. N. NISHIKIDO, Y. MOROI, H. UEHERA and R. MATUURA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, 47, 2634.
4. A. S. C. LAWRENCE and J. T. PEARSON, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1967, 63, 495.
5. H. N. SINGH and S. SWARUP, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1978, 51, 1534.
6. M. MANABE and M. CODA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn*, 1978, 51, 1599.
7. C. TREINER and R. BURY, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1978, 56, 2940.
8. Y. C. JEAN and H. J. ACHE, *J. Phys. Chem*, 1978, 82, 811.
9. C. McDONALD, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1970, 22, 744.
10. A. RAY, *J. Am. Chem. Soc*, 1969, 91, 6511.
11. A. RAY, *Nature (London)*, 1971, 231, 313.
12. C. McDONALD, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1967, 19, 411.
13. C. McDONALD, *J. Pharm. Pharmacol.*, 1970, 22, 148.
14. R. GOPAL and J. R. SINGH, *Kolloid Z*, 1970, 29, 669.
15. R. GOPAL and J. R. SINGH, *J. Phys. Chem*, 1973, 77, 554.
16. R. GOPAL and J. R. SINGH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, 49, 667.
17. R. GOPAL and J. R. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 800.
18. H. N. SINGH, S. SINGH and K. C. TEWARI, *J. Am Oil Chem. Soc.* 1975, 52, 436.
19. H. N. SINGH, S. M. SALEEM, R. P. SINGH and K. S. BIRDI, *J. Phys. Chem*, 1980, 84, 2191.
20. A. B. MANDAL, S. RAY, A. M. BISWAS and S. P. MOULIK, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1980, 84, 856.
21. R. DELISI, G. PERRON, J. PAQUETT and J. E. DESNOYERS, *Can J. Chem*, 1981, 59, 1865.
22. E. F. J. DUYNSTEE and E. GRUNWALD, *J. Am Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 4542.
23. E. EIGFNBERGER, *J. Prakt. Chem*, 1931, 130, 75.
24. J. H. FENDLER and E. J FENDLER, "Catalysis in Micellar and Macromolecular Systems", Academic Press, New York, 1977.
25. L. G. IONESEU, T. TOKUHIRO and B. J. CZERNIAWSKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, 52, 922.
26. P. BECHER, *J. Colloid Sci.*, 1965, 20, 728.
27. M. J. SCHICK and A. H. GILBERT, *J. Colloid Sci*, 1965, 20, 2431.
28. G. D. PARFITT and J. A. WOOD, *Kolloid Z. Z. Polym.*, 1969, 229, 55.
29. R. G. BATES and R. A. ROBINSON in "Chemical Physics of Ionic Solutions", eds. B. E. CONWAY and R. G. BARNADAS, Wiley, New York, 1966, p. 211.
30. T. L. FABRAY and R. M. FUOSS, *J. Phys. Chem*, 1964, 68, 971.
31. R. G. LE BEL and D. A. I. GORING, *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 1962, 7, 100.
32. E. WILHELM, R. BATTINO and R. J. WILCOCK, *Chem Rev.*, 1977, 77, 219.
33. G. C. KRESHECK, H. SCHNEIDER and H. A. SECHARAGA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1965, 69, 3132.
34. N. MULLER and T. W. JOHNSON, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1969, 73, 2042.
35. N. MULLER and F. E. PLATKO, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, 75, 547.
36. N. MULLER and H. SIMSOHN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1971, 75, 942.
37. C. TANFORD in "Micellization, Solubilization and Microemulsions," ed. K. L. MITTAL, Plenum Press, New York, 1979, Vol. 1, p. 119.
38. S. MIYAGISHI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, 48, 2349.
39. D. B. WETLAUFER, S. K. MALIK, L. STROLLER and R. L. COFFIN, *J. Am Chem. Soc*, 1964, 86, 508.
40. C. TANFORD and Y. NOZAKI, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1965, 290, 3568.
41. C. TREINER and A. LE BESNERAIS, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1977, 73, 44.